

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract: This article sheds light on a number of difficulties and problems in teaching and learning English and the methods and methods of finding solutions to them.

Key words: foreign language, activity, problems in language learning, educational games, solutions to problems.

Аннотация: Данная статья проливает свет на ряд трудностей и проблем в преподавании и изучении английского языка, а также методы и способы их решения.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, деятельность, проблемы изучения языка, развивающие игры, решение проблем.

Introduction. Today, the number of languages spoken in the world is about 600. They are developed from each other and can form unique family trees. Among them, one of those belonging to the German language family is English. One of the urgent issues of the present time is to teach foreign languages as a second language and educate the young generation in the spirit of universal human values such as love for the motherland, loyalty, high pride, and national pride. In our country, for the last 2-3 years, the young generation has been mainly involved in learning English and they are required to obtain a B1 or C1 level certificate and IELTS diploma. The goal is for all the future generations of our Motherland to learn foreign languages as if they were our mother tongue, to master the modern technologies of the developing world without any obstacles. In addition, in the period of the development of information communications of the 21st century, the introduction of new words, terms and expressions from one language to another has become a natural state. This situation, together with the enrichment and development of the language, sheds light on such features as the ability to replace incoming new words with the corresponding word or word in the Uzbek language or to find an alternative meaning. At the same time, teaching English as a foreign language is a very difficult task, especially in places where English serves a very limited purpose. And here the question may arise: "Why are there some difficulties and problems in learning English?" The reason is the current students' lack of vocabulary, low concentration, lack of discipline, boredom and speech problems, including insufficient exposure to English, insufficiently equipped auditoriums and lack of qualified teachers.

Main body. The task of English teachers is not only to teach learners or to focus more on their English language skills, such as reading, writing, listening and speaking, but also to instill in them a passion for English, it also consists of helping and encouraging by giving good attitude and great motivation. Despite this, teachers today face a number of difficulties and obstacles in teaching English. These are the following:

1. Auditorium environment. The environment is very important in teaching and learning English. A disturbing atmosphere in the auditorium distracts students and negatively

affects language learning. A suitable and comfortable environment is the main need for teaching English. If the environment is not suitable and comfortable for the students, it will destroy the English language learning process. In teaching English, mainly teachers face such an unfavorable environment.

2. Limited teaching resources. Teaching anything, not just English, depends on many resources. Teachers often face such problems. That is, teachers are not provided with enough resources to learn English effectively. Without them, it will be very difficult to teach and learn the language. Resources include speakers, microphones, projectors, computer systems, and other types of digital devices. With these, teaching and learning will be more effective and interesting.

3. The number of students in the auditorium. The presence of a large number of students in the auditorium causes a lot of anxiety and stress for teachers. Because in order to teach a large number of students, teachers have to work harder.

Problems that arise on the part of many students are as follows:

1. They make noise and disturb the teacher.
2. It will be difficult to manage the students in the audience.
3. It will be very difficult to attract a large number of students to study.
4. Educational resources will not be enough for all students.

5. Limited time. Time is very important in learning and teaching English. Teachers need time to observe their students and teach them at their level. However, there is very little class time allocated for teaching this subject. This is a very difficult task for teachers to teach in a short time.

6. The fact that students are attached to teachers. Another notable problem that teachers face is that students are completely dependent on teachers. They do not try to learn and speak themselves. Students always turn to teachers to help them learn and give them the right answers. They do not try to correct words and sentences when speaking English. In this problem, students have not learned the technical terms of using different tenses and words in English.

7. Students who are bored and not interested in learning English. Students' boredom and lack of interest in learning English is also a problem faced by teachers. Sometimes students are not interested in learning English and attending lectures. Then they try to engage in other activities. Sometimes they disturb the teachers by talking to others during the lecture and doing other meaningless things.

Along with problems and difficulties, of course, there are no solutions to them. The following are the best solutions:

1. Educational competitions in auditoriums. Competitions play a very important role in learning English. It forces students to learn English, such as debates, quizzes, etc. Various competitions among students make learning English interesting and encourage them to participate in competitions and win among their colleagues. Competitions make teaching English easier for teachers. Teachers should organize competition activities among students.

2. Using multimedia during the lecture. Often English teachers use old and traditional methods in teaching. But new devices and gadgets designed specifically for educational purposes can improve English teaching and learning. Teachers should use multimedia tools in their lectures. It makes learning English more interesting and understandable for students.

Because instead of written in books, students can easily understand the idea through visual images, videos, sounds, etc.

3. Teaching through games. Games are the most engaging activity for students. Games also play a very important role in education and learning. There are many educational games that can be played with students in Auditoriums. Games help to increase vocabulary. There is a game of placing the missing word in different types of sentences. This builds a lot of vocabulary. Students understand the types of words and their meanings and their placement in sentences. In the process of learning English, teachers should use the Auditorium to play games.

4. Manage lesson and timetable rules. Teachers should make rules and schedule of auditoriums, students should follow them. Rules and discipline play a very important role in learning English. Students must turn off their cell phones, not talk to their peers, come to class on time, and complete homework assignments on time and submit them to the teacher. If students violate any of its rules, they should be fined or their parents should be contacted.

Conclusion. Educating the current young generations and making them highly competent is not only the teacher's duty, but also depends on the family environment and the attention of the neighborhood. Scientific studies and researches show that 70% of all the information that a person receives during his life before the age of 6 shows the importance of preschool education in the development of a child's personality.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. At the meeting held by Mirziyoev on August 16, 2017, in order to determine measures for 100% inclusion of 5-6 year old children in preschool educational institutions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on" was adopted. And in these institutions, it was decided to teach English from an early age. The reason is, as our ancestors used to say, "the knowledge acquired in youth is a pattern carved in stone." This is not for nothing, as shown in this article, the earlier learning begins, it will lead to the elimination of some of the above-mentioned problems and difficulties, and the easier acquisition of language skills and competencies. it is. Especially if this knowledge, skills, skills are absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child develops foreign languages as naturally as his mother tongue. Educational games not only form knowledge, skills and abilities in a child, but at the same time, they ensure the child's healthy physical development, mentally refresh, strengthen self-confidence, and have a great opportunity to form social relations with others. it gives mak.

At the same time, the existing problems in language teaching indicated in this article, that is, the problems between teachers and young generations, can be eliminated based on the mentioned solutions.

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